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Cryoablation and Cryolocalization in the Prevention, Prognosis, Diagnosis, Imaging, Screening, Treatment and Management of Breast Cancer

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Abstract

Unprecedented studies have shown that slow-growing breast cancers can be treated with highly targeted tumor cryopreservation technology without the need for surgery. Experiments show that this method is effective in women with low-risk breast cancer over the age of 60. Cryoablation is a solution that eliminates breast tumors safely, quickly and painlessly or without the need for surgery. Takes. This method exposes the patient's tissues to severe cold to remove them without the need for anesthesia in the clinic. The new study, which involved about 200 women, found that after eliminating low-risk breast cancer, patients were left without cancer for three years. This treatment can be used to treat cancers of the bone, kidney, prostate and other types. Unlike lumpectomy or mastectomy, which involves removing the breast from the body, cryoectomy or cryopreservation of tumors preserve breast size, reduce the risk of infection and prevent scarring, and allow patients to function normally quickly, the researchers said. Resume yourself.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues, Tumors; Prevention, Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

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Introduction

Dietary fiber, which is abundant in whole grains (whole grains) of vegetables and fruits, can help prevent breast cancer. California South University (CSU) researchers conducted a study on more than 44 women who found that girls who ate more than They consumed 28 grams of dietary fiber in high school, compared to girls who consumed less than 15 grams of dietary fiber per day, 13 percent less likely to develop breast cancer. Causes a decrease in the hormone "estrogen" in the blood; an issue that may increase the growth of some cancer cells. The recommended amount of dietary fiber can be achieved through breakfast. In addition to eating whole-grain breads and five regular servings of vegetables and fruits, wheat bran, flaxseed, and all whole grains (grains whose bran and sprouts are not separated) are also high in fiber. Previous studies at California South University (CSU) have shown the importance of following a vegetarian diet to prevent breast cancer; because yellow plant pigments known as "carotenoids" can reduce the risk of breast cancer. These pigments are found in fruits, vegetables, yellow, red and green. Eating plenty of vegetables and fruits helps maintain weight, which is also a very important factor in preventing cancer, especially after menopause [1-510].

Results and Discussion

Although the exact cause of breast cancer has not yet been identified, there are several factors involved in the development of this disease, including: 1- Increasing age only 10 to 15% of breast cancers are seen in women under 40 years of age. While women over 60 are more prone to this disease. 2- Family history People with a history of breast cancer among their first-degree family members are twice as likely as others. 3- Gene mutations some inherited gene mutations increase the chances of getting this cancer. Genetic tests show the incidence of genetic problems, especially in people with a

family history. Predisposing factors: Obesity, especially abdominal fat, sedentary lifestyle and poor diet, glandular tissue and dense fat in the breast, infertility or pregnancy in old age (35 years) or in other words, the first pregnancy after the age of 30 and long-term use of hormones are among the predisposing factors. Breast cancer. Symptoms of breast cancer: Swelling of all or part of the breast, Cavity Cavitation of the skin (similar to orange peel), the pain, Nipple indentation, Redness, scaling or thickening of the breast skin and Secretion A sure way to diagnose One of the best and most accurate screening methods in diagnosing breast cancer is mammography. Mammography with advanced devices with low radiation, without any complications is able to detect intangible masses and calcareous deposits that form before cancer. Self-examination for early detection: look: In some cases, breast cancer causes changes in its appearance that can be detected by looking; therefore, you need to be familiar with the appearance of your body to be able to detect any possible changes. 1- Hang your hands on both sides of your body. 2- Pull the arms straight up from the side of your head. 3- Bend the hands from the elbows and press to the waist (press the hands to the waist and press). 4- Pull the arms straight forward and bend slightly forward. Take seriously any abnormal changes such as redness, dents and scaling, deviations or bumps. Touch: It is better to use the end of the last paragraph of the middle three fingers. Never squeeze the breast tissue between your fingers, as you will falsely feel the mass. While there really is no mass. The area between the collarbone from above, the sternum and armpit bones on both sides, and two fingers below the lower edge of the chest at the lower extremity elastic should be examined. ways of prevention: Choosing a healthy lifestyle, Smoking cessation, Weight control, Proper physical activity, Breastfeeding Pregnancy at the right age (20 to 35 years), healthy diet, reduce exposure to laboratory radiation, Limit hormonal therapies, consume a

variety of vitamins and nutrients and Adequate sleep and avoid stress.

Conclusions

The importance of recognizing the protrusions inside the breasts as soon as possible has always been emphasized. But did you know that breast cancer has lesser-known symptoms that may not be detected on personal examination or mammography? In the following, we will get acquainted with these symptoms. Discharge from the nipple an abnormal discharge from the nipple can be a sign of a breast problem. A discharge from the nipple that is bloody or pink and generally from only one breast is probably a sign of breast cancer, especially if the discharge is persistent. Skin changes Skin changes are one of the most common lesser-known symptoms of breast cancer. Thickening or redness of the skin, along with a slight puffiness like orange peel is a sign. In this case, like orange peel, small holes are seen at the site of hair follicles. Skin changes such as thickening, piercing, and discoloration of the skin can be signs of breast cancer. Nipple scaling Redness, scaling or dryness and tightness of the nipple or ring around it may be a sign of Paget's disease, which can be an early sign of breast cancer. Skin changes on the nipples are often more like benign problems such as eczema or psoriasis, but the traditional treatments used for these problems do not work and instead get worse. Chest deformity or enlargement Enlarged breasts - especially if only one breast is swollen - or deformed breasts can be a sign of a problem with breast tissue. Breast deformity so that the overall shape of the breast is abnormal and there is a bulge in one part of the breast can be a sign of cancer. It may be like a bulge or just a part of the breast that is tighter and you do not feel a lump inside when you touch it. Also, this bulge or stiffness is more pronounced in most cases when the body is in other positions. You go nipple flattening or sagging of the nipple or changing its direction can be a sign of breast cancer. In this case, the

nipple is placed in a different direction and position instead of being straight out or down. Flattening or sagging of the nipple is another sign of Paget's disease. Red or hot spots the presence of red or hot spots on the breast, which sometimes cover the entire breast, can be a sign of breast cancer. Although red or hot spots can be a sign of mastitis or a breast infection - an infectious disease that often occurs during breastfeeding - mastitis is usually accompanied by fever. If the red or hot spots are not accompanied by fever and are persistent and do not improve, it could mean breast cancer.

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Scattering (FXS), Wide-Angle X-Ray Scattering (WAXS), Grazing-Incidence Small-Angle X-Ray Scattering (GISAXS), Grazing-Incidence Wide-Angle X-Ray Scattering (GIWAXS), Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS), Grazing-Incidence Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (GISANS), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), Wide-Angle X-Ray Diffraction (WAXD), Grazing-Incidence X-Ray Diffraction (GIXD) and Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Diffraction (EDXRD) Comparative Study on Malignant and Benign Human Cancer Cells and Tissues under Synchrotron Radiation. *Glob Imaging Insights*. 3: 1-10.

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Cancer Nano Drugs, Nano Drugs Delivery, ATR-FTIR Spectroscopy, Raman Spectroscopy, Intelligent Molecules, Molecular Dynamics, Biosensors, Biomarkers, Molecular Diagnostics, Numerical Chemistry, Nucleic Acids, DNA/RNA Monitoring, DNA/RNA Hypermethylation & Hypomethylation, Human Cancer Tissues, Human Cancer Cells, Tumors, Cancer Tissues, Cancer Cells, etc. He has participated at more than five hundred reputed international conferences, seminars, congresses, symposiums and forums around the world as yet. Also, he possesses many published articles in Science Citation Index (SCI)/International Scientific Indexing (ISI), Medline/PubMed and Scopus Journals. It should be noted that he has visited many universities or scientific and academic research institutes in different countries such as United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Scotland, Ireland, Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Luxembourg, Romania, Greece, Russia, Estonia, Ukraine, Turkey, France, Swiss, Germany, Sweden, Norway, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, South Africa, Egypt, Brazil, Spain, Portugal, Mexico, Japan, Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Philippines, South Korea, China, India, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, etc. as research fellow, sabbatical and volunteer researcher or visitor and so on heretofore. He has a history of several years of teaching for college students and various disciplines and trends in different universities. Moreover, he has been a senior advisor in various industry and factories. He is expert in many computer programs and programming languages. Hitherto, he has authored more than twenty books and book chapters in different fields of Chemistry. Syne, he has been awarded more than one thousand reputed international awards, prizes, scholarships and honors. Heretofore, he has multiple editorial duties in many reputed international and peer-reviewed journals, books and publishers. Hitherward, he is a member of

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